

«TEACHER CREATIVE ACTIVITY IN THE FACILITATIVE APPROACH: ITS EFFECT ON STUDENT’S MOTIVATION».

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Annotation. *The study investigates the impact of teachers’ creative activity within the facilitative approach on students’ academic motivation. Creative activity is considered a multifaceted cognitive and creative resource that enables the generation of educational situations, individualization of the learning process, and adaptation of teaching methods to students’ needs. The empirical part of the study examined the relationship between teachers’ creative activity, their preference for a facilitative pedagogical communication style, and game-based interaction methods with changes in students’ motivation. Results indicate that the use of creative activity and facilitative approaches positively influences achievement and self-development motivation, whereas the absence of such methods is associated with negative trends in cognitive motivation, self-esteem, and an increase in amotivation. The findings highlight the integrative role of teacher creative activity as both a cognitive and motivational regulator in the educational process.*

Key words: *teacher creative activity, facilitative teaching style, pedagogical communication, student motivation, game-based learning.*

The phenomenon of imagination and teacher creative activity is a multi-level issue: first, the complexity and ambiguity of defining the concepts themselves; second, the need to differentiate them from other cognitive processes, as they are closely connected with thinking, perception, and memory; third, insufficient study of key aspects of teacher imagination and creative activity for effective pedagogical communication.

In professional teaching activity, imagination and creative activity perform several functions:

1. Ability to create mental images.

Imagination allows teachers to form and visualize images and sensations, including real objects, events, and abstract concepts. Mental images support the formation of abstract concepts, linking new information with existing representations, and develop students’ creative imagination. A lack of visualization and goal-setting skills may hinder planning and goal orientation.

2. Role of teacher’s creative potential.

A teacher’s creative potential plays a key role in motivating students and solving pedagogical problems, enabling the synthesis and generation of ideas, images, and concepts. The ability to develop students’ creative potential transforms learning activities, enhancing intrinsic motivation and engagement. A lack of creative potential prevents the implementation of developmental learning in the modern global educational context.

3. Volitional aspect of imagination.

This includes awareness of how willpower and self-control affect the creation and management of mental images. A teacher who can exercise willpower to develop images even in difficult situations is a creative personality. The volitional aspect motivates students to seek knowledge and achieve learning goals, ensuring an individualized approach.

4. Emotional component of imagination.

Emotions influence the content and nature of imagined images. Empathy allows teachers to provide constructive feedback, considering students' individual characteristics and emotional states. A lack of emotional support leads to negative attitudes toward learning, lower achievement, and difficulties in social adaptation.

5. Imagination as experimentation and improvisation.

This involves modifying learning materials, combining new methods, and adapting the educational process to students' needs and interests. Improvisation develops teachers' cognitive flexibility and ability to adjust plans to unforeseen situations.

6. Imagination as anticipatory thinking.

V.T. Kudryavtsev states: “By imagining, a person instantly penetrates the essence, the basis of the developing integrity of the object even before a clear concept forms in his consciousness” (Kudryavtsev, 2016, p.62). Imagination allows forecasting possible outcomes and scenarios, saving resources and planning actions effectively.

Key reasons for the necessity of teacher creative activity:

1. A creative approach to teaching

Imagination helps teachers develop and combine original teaching methods, which will affect how effectively students learn the material. This will allow for the creation of adaptive lessons, where teachers, based on observation and diagnosis, design teaching materials based on the dominant abilities of each student.

2. Student motivation

Student motivation is closely related to the extent to which the teacher can personalise and enliven the learning material. Teachers who use their creative imagination are able to make the learning process exciting, emotionally rich and focused on the personal interests of students. Imagination helps teachers maintain interest in the subject by using unconventional approaches to explaining complex topics, using multimedia or visual teaching materials.

3. Solving pedagogical problems

Imagination plays an important role in solving various pedagogical problems and issues, especially in the educational and playful form of communication that the teacher is facing. Imagination helps to find new methods of interacting with students, cope with conflict situations, and adapt to changing conditions in the educational process.

Game-based elements and facilitative style

The activity of the learner should become the basis for achieving the developmental goals of education – ‘knowledge is not transferred in a ready-made form, but is constructed by the students themselves in the process of cognitive and research activities’ (Asmolov, 2008, p. 10). V. A. Slastenin emphasises that the uniqueness of the teaching profession consists in its humanistic, collective and creative nature (Slastenin, 2013, p. 61). In this context, the creative imagination of the teacher becomes a necessary condition for the successful solution of key pedagogical tasks, including effective socialisation, education and personal development of students.

Game-based elements and the development of imagination in collaborative learning activities become not only means of increasing motivation, but also important components of learning activities that contribute to the development of a child's personality in the context of modern digital society. A.G. Asmolov notes that as soon as A.N. Leontiev addresses the issue of the connection between ethics and psychology, axiology and psychology, he turns his attention to the most important problems of psychology – the problems of personality development and education, which should generate personality rather than be a ‘factory of society's blinded minds’. A.N. Leontiev emphasises the danger associated with the excessive accumulation of information without its comprehension, calling it ‘ethical diagnosis of depersonalisation’ (Cited from: Asmolov, 2008).

Play primarily involves joint activity, without which the further development and formation of socially useful activity in adolescents is impossible. Despite the standard concepts of pedagogical communication that have become established in educational practice, the current period of uncertainty dictates its own criteria and requires a review of the educational process. In the traditional understanding of TAT – ‘Teacher Active Time’ – prevails over SAT – ‘Students Active Time’ (Scrivener, 2009, p. 17).

P.G. Shchedrovitsky uses the term ‘collective thinking’ emphasising the need for communication and cooperation skills with ‘the Other’ who uses different knowledge, possesses different prototypes of activity organisation, and is oriented towards different ideas and values. The term ‘transprofessionalism’ is also relevant, which refers not to a set of professional knowledge in one field, but to the willingness and ability to fully engage in and organize collective thinking (Shchedrovitsky, 2021, p. 303). In this context, the facilitative style of pedagogical communication takes on particular significance. Here, a parallel can be drawn with L.S. Vygotsky's theory of the ‘zone of proximal development’ where the teacher plays the role not only of an informant but also of a guide, helping students move forward and reach new milestones in their development. P.G. Shchedrovitsky sees the modern teacher as a ‘tutor’ who guides students in the process of thinking and activity. The tutor helps students connect theoretical knowledge with practical tasks by participating in real projects and research (Shchedrovitsky, 2021, p. 381).

The facilitator controls the dynamics in the classroom so that the presence of other students becomes a stimulus for cooperation rather than a source of stress. T.Y. Bazarov noted that cooperativeness is a characteristic competence of a facilitator. The main goal is to achieve high efficiency in group activities (Bazarov, 2013, p. 94).

The term facilitation was introduced into pedagogy thanks to the work of American psychologist Carl Ransom Rogers in the mid-20th century and had a significant impact on pedagogical theory and practice, especially in the context of the development of humanistic education. Carl Ransom Rogers suggested that the role of the teacher should be supportive rather than authoritarian, believing that learning is facilitated when the learner ‘...chooses the direction themselves, helps to discover their own learning resources, formulates and solves problems, lives with the consequences of that choice, then meaningful learning becomes maximised’ (Rogers, 1983, p. 162). According to Rogers' humanistic concept, the facilitative style requires the teacher to be empathetic, flexible, and responsive to changes in the learning dynamic. A teacher who creates an atmosphere of trust, openness, and empathy in the learning process helps students feel comfortable expressing their thoughts and ideas, and the learning process itself becomes meaningful (Rogers, Freberg, 2019, p. 352).

One of the key ideas of the ‘facilitative’ teaching style is to encourage independent learning, where each student is personally responsible for their own educational path. Consequently, the teacher-facilitator will encourage students to ask questions, critically evaluate information, and form their own opinions. Working in groups, students learn to cooperate, listen to each other, and solve problems together. Michael Wilkinson notes the humanistic component of facilitation – caring for people, the desire to help, putting one's ego aside – and also believes that ‘facilitation is a skill rather than a role’ (Wilkinson, 2012, p. 46). The facilitative style of pedagogical communication requires a high level of involvement, creative activity, and self-analysis from the teacher. Facilitation creates an environment for the free expression of thoughts and feelings, which is a key component of co-creation, where students can develop both their emotional and cognitive abilities.

Empirical part of the study

The empirical part of this study substantiated and tested hypotheses about the existence of correlations between the level of creative activity of teachers, their preference for a facilitation style of pedagogical communication, and game-based forms of interaction. The influence of the above factors on the learning motivation of schoolchildren was also analysed. The analysis and interpretation of the results were carried out from the perspectives of cultural-historical, activity-based, and human-centred approaches, based on the methodological foundations of L.S. Vygotsky, A.N. Leontiev, C. Rogers, D.B. Elkonin, and V.V. Davydov.

In order to compare and justify the effectiveness of the facilitation programme, an analysis of school motivation was conducted in two groups, comparing the school motivation indicators of the experimental groups before and after the use of facilitation techniques and comparing them with the data of the control groups that refused to participate in the facilitation programme. In the experimental schools, a training facilitation programme was conducted for teachers, who were required to actively apply facilitation methods in their lessons for two months. The study included teachers and students from public and private secondary schools.

Teachers:

A total of 90 teachers participated in the study: public schools – 47 respondents (52.2%)
private schools – 43 respondents (47.8%)

The mean age of the teachers was 39.48 years (SD = 10.77).

The average teaching experience was 13.6 years (SD = 10.20).

In terms of gender, 82.2% were women (n = 74) and 17.8% were men (n = 16).

Students:

A total of 250 students participated in the study: public schools – 102 respondents
(40.8%)

private schools – 148 respondents (59.2%)

The age of the students ranged from 11 to 15 years (M = 13.61, SD = 1.7).

Gender distribution: 133 girls (53.2%) and 117 boys (46.8%).

The aim of the multi-level study is to assess the changes in student motivation before and after the training of teachers who completed the programme and those who did not, without using facilitation techniques in class.

Wilcoxon's statistical criterion is used to test the significance of changes in motivation by comparing the differences in ranks between paired values (before and after). Wilcoxon's cross-tabulation analysis allows us to identify significant shifts in motivation, if any, by comparing the

ranks of differences between paired values. It is important to note that different indicators have different levels of significance for private and public schools.

Table 1. Indicators of variables in experimental schools in comparative analysis using the Wilcoxon criterion (at $p \leq 0.05$)

Variables in experimental schools	Indicator	Number	Average rank after/before	Level of significance
Cognitive motivation	Decrease	2	10,00	0,072
	Increase	11	6,45	
	No change	8		
Achievement motivation	Decrease	2	9,25	0,017
	Increase	13	7,81	
	No change	6		
Self-development motivation	Decrease	2	8,00	0,037
	Increase	11	6,82	
	No change	8		

Table 1 shows the cognitive motivation of students in experimental schools: the changes are not significant (significance level $0.072 > 0.05$), confirming that motivation in this category has not changed, remaining at a positive level. There is a significant improvement in achievement motivation of 0.017. In experimental schools, there is also a statistically significant increase in self-development motivation (significance level $0.037 < 0.05$), confirming the positive impact of the facilitation method.

Variables in control schools	Indicator	Number	Average rank after/before	Significance level
Cognitive motivation	Decrease	13	7,73	,002
	Increase	1	4,50	
	No change	7		
Self-development motivation	Decrease	6	4,08	,058
	Increase	1	3,50	
	No change	14		
Self-esteem motivation	Decrease	8	5,25	,018
	Increase	1	3,00	
	No change	12		
Positive external motivation	Decrease	2	3,50	,006
	Increase	11	7,64	
	No change	8		
Amotivation	Decrease	2	4,00	,008
	Increase	11	7,55	
	No change	8		

Table 2. Indicators of variables in control schools in comparative analysis using the Wilcoxon criterion (at $p \leq 0.05$)

According to the Table 2, there is a significant decrease in cognitive motivation (significance level $0.002 < 0.05$) among students in control schools, indicating a statistically significant decrease in this category.

- Self-esteem motivation: statistically significant negative changes with a significance level of $0.018 < 0.05$.

- Positive external motives: a statistically significant increase in external motivation (significance level $0.006 < 0.05$) indicates that external stimuli, namely the desire to receive positive grades at the end of the school year, significantly influence this motivation.

- The level of amotivation increased significantly. The significance level of $0.008 < 0.05$ indicates significant changes in the dynamics of ‘amotivation’ and, according to the data, in a negative direction.

Conclusions from the analysis

Experimental schools:

- Following by the results, the facilitation educational programme had a statistically significant impact on improving the achievement motivation and self-development motivation of schoolchildren.

Control schools:

- In this group, the most pronounced negative changes occurred in cognitive motivation and amotivation, while positive external motivation showed an improvement in dynamics.

The results show that imagination acts not only as a cognitive resource for designing teaching methods, but also as a regulator of educational interaction. In the “teacher-facilitation-student” system, creative imagination performs an integrative function: from generating educational situations to forming a dialogue space.

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